

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

The FAIR, CARE and TRUST principles and their applicability to various research objects, including data, software, metadata and hardware.

RDA 21st PLENARY SESSIONS

- Breakout 1: Metadata IG: [Structuring Semantic Information with Respect to Conventional Metadata \(Syntactic\) Structures](#)
- Breakout 1: Software Source Code IG: [Mastering the Art of Research Software Metadata and Metrics](#)
- Breakout 2: Ethics and Social Aspects of Data IG: [Identifying and discussing key topics in ethics for the RDA Community: Developing together a revised agenda for the Ethical and Social Aspects of Data \(ESAD\) Interest Group](#)
- Breakout 2: Birds of a Feather: [Very Large Open Datasets for Machine Learning in Personalized Medicine](#)
- Breakout 2: RDA / CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG: [Advancing the RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG](#)
- Breakout 3: Birds of a Feather: [NTRO Gaggles - Boosting non text support through experiential and collaborative effort](#)
- Breakout 3: Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation (AIDV) WG: [Transforming the AIDV-WG's deliverables into horizontal actions across data disciplines, sectors, and systems: Engaging digital communities in incorporating ELSI in data and AI tools and systems for achieving the UN SDGs and real-world outcomes](#)
- Breakout 3: Birds of a Feather: [The Way to FAIR: From the instrument to the researcher -- Calibrating the ecosystem](#)
- Breakout 3: Complex Citations WG: [Complex Citations: Next steps towards a Demonstration Prototype](#)
- Breakout 4: FAIR for Machine Learning (FAIR4ML) IG: [Building towards FAIR for Machine Learning](#)

- Breakout 4: Birds of a Feather: [Let's talk about FAIR mappings! Towards common practices for sharing mappings and crosswalks](#)
- Breakout 4: Birds of a Feather: [Bridging the Data/HPC divide: lessons learned from the community talks](#)
- Breakout 5: FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG: [FAIR Digital Object Fabric: Shaping the Fabric](#)
- Breakout 5: 2nd Birds of a Feather: [Trusted / Secure Research Environments for Sensitive / Confidential Data: FAIRness for "Closed" Data and Processes](#)
- Breakout 6: PID IG: [Equity and Inclusion: universal access to PIDs](#)
- Breakout 6: RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories IG: [TRUST Principles and Repository Certification Landscape](#)

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RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) WG](#)
- [Blockchain Applications in Health WG](#)
- [CoreTrustSeal Maintenance WG](#)
- [CURE-FAIR WG](#)
- [Ethics and Social Aspects of Data IG](#)
- [FAIR Data Maturity Model WG](#)
- [FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG](#)
- [FAIR for Research Software \(FAIR4RS\) WG](#)
- [FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG](#)
- [FAIR Principles for Research Hardware](#)
- [International Indigenous Data Sovereignty IG](#)
- [PID IG](#)
- [Raising FAIRness in health data and health research performing organisations \(HRPOs\) WG](#)
- [RDA / CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG](#)
- [RDA COVID-19](#)
- [RDA Privacy Implications of Research Data Sets IG](#)

RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

doi: <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00094>

'FAIR, CARE, TRUST - Principles' cont.

Research Data Alliance Pathways

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/rdas-21st-plenary-programme>

Version: July 2023

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The FAIR, CARE and TRUST principles and their applicability to various research objects, including data, software, metadata and hardware.

RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories IG](#)
- [Reproducible Health Data Services WG](#)
- [Social Science Research Data IG](#)
- [Software Source Code IG](#)
- [Virtual Research Environment IG \(VRE-IG\)](#)

☀ [See all RDA groups](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research](#)
- [A Fresh Look at FAIR for Research Software](#)
- [A Survey on Adoption Guidelines for the FAIR4RS Principles](#)
- [Array Database Assessment Recommendations](#)
- [Challenges of Curating for Reproducible and FAIR Research Output](#)
- [FAIR Data Maturity Model specification and guidelines](#)
- [FAIR Principles for Research Software \(FAIR4RS Principles\)](#)
- [FAIR4RS Adoption support](#)
- [Health Research Performing Organisations \(HRPOs\) FAIR Guidelines](#)
- [RDA Data Usage Metrics WG Recommendations](#)
- [Summary of Virtual Layer Recommendations](#)
- [The FAIR4RS Team Working Together to Make Research Software FAIR](#)
- [Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things](#)
- [Use cases and identifier schemes for persistent software source code identification \(V1.1\)](#)

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RDA DOMAIN AMBASSADOR

Allyson Lister

RDA/EOSC Future Domain Ambassador for standards, repositories and policies

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A Decade of Data 2013-2023
Research Data Alliance

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'FAIR, CARE, TRUST - Adoption, Implementation & Deployment'

Research Data Alliance Pathways

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THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Practices and methods for the adoption, implementation and deployment of the FAIR, CARE and TRUST Principles.

RDA 21ST PLENARY SESSIONS

- Breakout 1: Birds of a Feather: [Why aren't we talking about Collections as Data?](#)
- Breakout 1: ESIP/RDA Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences IG: [Where are the FAIR Earth, Space and Environmental Science Discipline Data Repositories?](#)
- Breakout 2: Vocabulary Services IG: [Building Collaborative Bridges: Fostering Collaborations within RDA](#)
- Breakout 2: RDA / CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG: [Advancing the RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG](#)
- Breakout 3: Birds of a Feather: [FAIRification of Genomic Tracks: data-driven life science through granular discovery of biological sequence annotations with uniform metadata](#)
- Breakout 3: Working with PIDs in Tools IG & National PID Strategies Interest Group: [PID Exchange - a curated information resource for PID adopters](#)
- Breakout 3: Research data needs of the Photon and Neutron Science community IG: [Tools and Methods working towards the FAIR Facility](#)
- Breakout 3: Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation (AIDV) WG: [Transforming the AIDV-WG's deliverables into horizontal actions across data disciplines, sectors, and systems: Engaging digital communities in incorporating ELSI in data and AI tools and systems for achieving the UN SDGs and real-world outcomes](#)
- Breakout 4: Birds of a Feather: [Wind energy community standards](#)
- Breakout 4: Birds of a Feather: [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy technical repository service providers](#)

- Breakout 4: Repository Platforms for Research Data IG & Domain Repositories IG: [Data Repositories Discovering Unpublished and Diverse Data Usage and Impact](#)
- Breakout 4: Birds of a Feather: [Let's talk about FAIR mappings! Towards common practices for sharing mappings and crosswalks](#)
- Breakout 4: Birds of a Feather: [Bridging the Data/HPC divide: lessons learned from the community talks](#)
- Breakout 5: FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG: [FAIR Digital Object Fabric: Shaping the Fabric](#)
- Breakout 6: Education and Training on Handling of Research Data IG: [Fiesta ETHRD-IG! Community celebration of education & training material and metadata richness](#)
- Breakout 6: Life Science Data Infrastructures IG: [Key aspects of FAIR for infrastructure solutions in the biomolecular life sciences](#)
- Breakout 6: PID IG: [Equity and Inclusion: universal access to PIDs](#)
- Breakout 6: RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories IG: [TRUST Principles and Repository Certification Landscape](#)
- Breakout 6: Birds of a Feather: [Describing Chemical, Physical and Biological samples digitally: Seeking harmonization](#)

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RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) WG](#)
- [Blockchain Applications in Health WG](#)
- [Brokering Framework Working Group](#)
- [CoreTrustSeal Maintenance WG](#)

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'FAIR, CARE, TRUST - Adoption, Implementation & Deployment' cont.

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THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Practices and methods for the adoption, implementation and deployment of the FAIR, CARE and TRUST Principles.

RELEVANT RDA GROUPS CONT.

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- [Data Conservation IG](#)
- [Data for Development IG](#)
- [Data Granularity WG](#)
- [Data policy standardisation and implementation IG](#)
- [Domain Repositories IG](#)
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- [FAIR Data Maturity Model WG](#)
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- [FAIR Principles for Research Hardware](#)
- [FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG](#)
- [Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology WG \(I-ADOPT WG\)](#)
- [Libraries for Research Data IG](#)
- [Life Science Data Infrastructures IG](#)
- [Metadata IG](#)
- [National PID Strategies Interest Group](#)
- [National PID Strategies WG](#)
- [PID IG](#)
- [RDA / CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG](#)

★ [See all RDA groups](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research](#)
- [A Fresh Look at FAIR for Research Software](#)
- [A Survey on Adoption Guidelines for the FAIR4RS Principles](#)
- [Challenges of Curating for Reproducible and FAIR Research Output](#)
- [Data Discovery Paradigms User Requirements and Recommendations for Data Repositories](#)
- [Developing a Research Data Policy Framework for All Journals and Publishers](#)
- [Eleven Quick Tips for Finding Research Data](#)
- [FAIR Principles for Research Software \(FAIR4RS Principles\)](#)
- [FAIR4RS Adoption support](#)
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- [Member survey on bridging the gap between funders and communities - perspectives on benefits and challenges of FAIR assessments V2.0](#)
- [Principles and best practices in data versioning for all data sets big and small](#)
- [RDA & CODATA Legal Interoperability Of Research Data Principles And Implementation Guidelines](#)
- [RDA Data Usage Metrics WG Recommendations](#)
- [Recommendations and Capacity Development Resource Kit](#)
- [Research Data Repository Interoperability Primer](#)
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- [Summary of Virtual Layer Recommendations](#)
- [Sustainable Business Models for Brokering Middleware to support Research Interoperability](#)
- [The FAIR4RS Team Working Together to Make Research Software FAIR](#)
- [The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations Interlinking Standards, Databases and Data Policies](#)
- [Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things](#)
- [Use cases and identifier schemes for persistent software source code identification \(V1.1\)](#)
- [WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG Outputs and Recommendations](#)

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RDA DOMAIN AMBASSADOR

Sara El-Gebali

RDA/EOSC Future Domain Ambassador for Life Science

📧 [Read more & contact](#)

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Research Data Alliance

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'Data Infrastructures & Environments - Institutional'

Research Data Alliance Pathways

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THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Workflows and methods to implement the FAIR, CARE and TRUST Principles at the institutional data infrastructure level.

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- Breakout 2: Research Data Architectures in Research Institutions IG: [Data Retention and Disposal infrastructure and policies](#)
- Breakout 2: Active Data Management Plans IG: [Active Data Management Plans: how far have we come in the changing landscape](#)
- Breakout 4: Birds of a Feather: [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy technical repository service providers](#)
- Breakout 5: GORC International Model WG & Global Open Research Commons IG: [Global open research commons: what it takes and the road to get there. Reflections and discussion on creating a commons attribute model and a commons integration roadmap](#)
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- [Sensitive Data Interest Group](#)
- [Skills and training curriculums to support FAIR research software IG](#)
- [Software Source Code IG](#)
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- [Data Discovery Paradigms User Requirements and Recommendations for Data Repositories](#)
- [Eleven Quick Tips for Finding Research Data](#)
- [Income Streams for Data Repositories](#)
- [RDA COVID-19 Guidelines and Recommendations \(draft versions\)](#)
- [RDA Data Usage Metrics WG Recommendations](#)
- [Report prepared at Plenary 3](#)
- [Summary of Virtual Layer Recommendations](#)
- [Sustainable Business Models for Brokering Middleware to support Research Interoperability](#)
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- [Use cases and identifier schemes for persistent software source code identification \(V1.1\)](#)

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RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [Complex Citations Working Group](#)
- [Data Citation WG](#)
- [Domain Repositories IG](#)
- [ESIP/RDA Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences IG](#)
- [Global Open Research Commons IG](#)
- [GORC International Model WG](#)
- [Preservation Tools, Techniques, and Policies](#)
- [Repository Core Description WG](#)
- [Repository Platforms for Research Data IG](#)
- [Research Data Architectures in Research Institutions IG](#)

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'Data Infrastructures & Environments - Regional and Disciplinary'

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THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Standards and practices specific to a region and disciplinary community.

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- Breakout 3: Research Data Management in Engineering IG & RDA/CODATA Materials Data, Infrastructure & Interoperability IG: [Engineering Terminology and Schema for LIMS](#)
- Breakout 4: Birds of a Feather: [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy technical repository service providers](#)
- Breakout 5: GORC International Model WG & Global Open Research Commons IG: [Global open research commons: what it takes and the road to get there. Reflections and discussion on creating a commons attribute model and a commons integration roadmap](#)
- Breakout 6: Life Science Data Infrastructures IG: [Key aspects of FAIR for infrastructure solutions in the biomolecular life sciences](#)

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- [RDA/CODATA Materials Data, Infrastructure & Interoperability IG](#)
- [Psychological Data IG](#)
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- [RDA-COVID19-Clinical](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Community-participation](#)
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- [RDA-COVID19-Social-Sciences](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Software](#)
- [Reproducible Health Data Services WG](#)
- [Research Data Management in Engineering IG](#)
- [Research data needs of the Photon and Neutron Science community IG](#)
- [Virtual Research Environment IG \(VRE-IG\)](#)
- [Working with PIDS in Tools](#)

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RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

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- [Chemistry Research Data IG](#)
- [Data Discovery Paradigms IG](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

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- [23 Things Physical Samples](#)
- [A Fresh Look at FAIR for Research Software](#)

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doi. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00094>

Data Infrastructures & Environments - Regional and Disciplinary cont.

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THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

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- [Report prepared at Plenary 3](#)
- [Summary of Virtual Layer Recommendations](#)

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'Data Infrastructures & Environments - International'

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THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Topics related to implementing principles that are common to all data infrastructures and community practices.

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- Breakout 1: Birds of a Feather: [Understanding and Capturing the Uptake of Digital Research Infrastructure](#)
- Breakout 1: Data Repository Attributes WG: [Recommended Descriptive Attributes for Data Repositories](#)
- Breakout 1: ESIP/RDA Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences IG: [Where are the FAIR Earth, Space and Environmental Science Discipline Data Repositories?](#)
- Breakout 2: Data Discovery Paradigms IG: [Ten recommendations for data repositories/catalogues to improve data discoverability](#)
- Breakout 2: Active Data Management Plans IG: [Active Data Management Plans: how far have we come in the changing landscape](#)
- Breakout 2: Birds of a Feather: [Very Large Open Datasets for Machine Learning in Personalized Medicine](#)
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- Breakout 3: Working with PIDs in Tools IG & National PID Strategies Interest Group: [PID Exchange - a curated information resource for PID adopters](#)
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- Breakout 4: Repository Platforms for Research Data IG & Domain Repositories IG: [Data Repositories Discovering Unpublished and Diverse Data Usage and Impact](#)
- Breakout 5: RDA-OfR Mapping the landscape of digital research tools WG: [Mapping the landscape of digital research tools working meeting](#)
- Breakout 5: GORC International Model WG, IG Global Open Research Commons IG: [Global open research commons: what it takes and the road to get there. Reflections and discussion on creating a commons attribute model and a commons integration roadmap](#)
- Breakout 5: FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG: [FAIR Digital Object Fabric: Shaping the Fabric](#)
- Breakout 6: PID IG: [Equity and Inclusion: universal access to PIDs](#)

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RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation \(AIDV\) WG](#)
- [Brokering Framework Working Group](#)
- [Complex Citations Working Group](#)
- [Data Discovery Paradigms IG](#)
- [Data for Development IG](#)
- [Data Granularity WG](#)
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'Data Infrastructures & Environments - International' cont.

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Topics related to implementing principles that are common to all data infrastructures and community practices.

RELEVANT RDA GROUPS CONT.

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- [FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG](#)
- [FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG](#)
- [Global Open Research Commons IG](#)
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- [Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology WG \(I-ADOPT WG\)](#)
- [Life Science Data Infrastructures IG](#)
- [Metadata IG](#)
- [National PID Strategies Interest Group](#)
- [National PID Strategies WG](#)
- [Physical Samples and Collections in the Research Data Ecosystem IG](#)
- [PID IG](#)
- [Preservation Tools, Techniques, and Policies](#)
- [Preserving Scientific Annotation WG](#)
- [RDA / CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG](#)
- [RDA-OfR Mapping the landscape of digital research tools WG](#)
- [RDA Privacy Implications of Research Data Sets IG](#)
- [RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories IG](#)
- [Repository Core Description WG](#)
- [Repository Platforms for Research Data IG](#)
- [Research data needs of the Photon and Neutron Science community IG](#)
- [Social Dynamics of Data Interoperability IG](#)
- [Social Science Research Data IG](#)
- [Software Source Code IG](#)
- [Virtual Research Environment IG \(VRE-IG\)](#)
- [Working Group on Ethical and Legal best practices for Drone Data in a global research context \(WELDD\)](#)
- [Working with PIDs in Tools IG](#)

☀ [See all RDA groups](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [Array Database Assessment Recommendations](#)
- [Challenges of Curating for Reproducible and FAIR Research Output](#)
- [Data Discovery Paradigms User Requirements and Recommendations for Data Repositories](#)
- [Eleven Quick Tips for Finding Research Data](#)
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'Training, Stewardship & Data Management Planning'

Research Data Alliance Pathways

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THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Training modules, schools, workshops and library support for stewardship and data management.

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- Breakout 2: Active Data Management Plans IG: [Active Data Management Plans: how far have we come in the changing landscape](#)
- Breakout 2: Ethics and Social Aspects of Data IG: [Identifying and discussing key topics in ethics for the RDA Community: Developing together a revised agenda for the Ethical and Social Aspects of Data \(ESAD\) Interest Group](#)
- Breakout 4: Engaging Researchers with Data IG: [Researchers' engagement with data management: from cookbook to toolkit](#)
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- Breakout 5: Linguistics Data IG: [Developing a Needs Analysis for Open Scholarship in Linguistics and the Language Sciences](#)
- Breakout 6: Education and Training on Handling of Research Data IG: [Fiesta ETHRD-IG! Community celebration of education & training material and metadata richness](#)

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RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

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- [DMP Common Standards WG](#)
- [CODATA/RDA Research Data Science Schools for Low and Middle Income Countries](#)
- [CURE-FAIR WG](#)
- [Discipline-specific Guidance for Data Management Plans WG](#)
- [Early Career and Engagement IG](#)
- [Engaging Researchers with Data IG](#)
- [Ethics and Social Aspects of Data IG](#)
- [Exposing Data Management Plans WG](#)
- [FAIR Data Maturity Model WG](#)
- [FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG](#)

RELEVANT RDA GROUPS CONT.

- [Libraries for Research Data IG](#)
- [Linguistics Data IG](#)
- [Professionalising Data Stewardship IG](#)
- [Psychological Data Community of Practice](#)
- [RDA Privacy Implications of Research Data Sets IG](#)
- [RDA/CODATA Summer Schools in Data Science and Cloud Computing in the Developing World WG](#)
- [Research Data Management in Engineering IG](#)
- [Skills and training curriculums to support FAIR research software IG](#)

 [See all RDA groups](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [23 Things Libraries for Research Data](#)
- [Core Characteristics of Learning Resource Collectors](#)
- [Engaging Researchers with Data Management The Cookbook](#)
- [Member survey on bridging the gap between funders and communities - perspectives on benefits and challenges of FAIR assessments V2.0](#)
- [RDA Professionalising Data Stewardship - Data Stewardship Landscape Initial Report](#)
- [Recommendations for a minimal metadata set to aid harmonised discovery of learning resources](#)
- [The FAIR4RS Team Working Together to Make Research Software FAIR](#)
- [The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations Interlinking Standards, Databases and Data Policies](#)

 [See all recommendations & outputs](#)

Celebrate a Decade of Data...

[Read more about the RDA's 10th Anniversary & see the event and activity series.](#)

A Decade of Data 2013-2023
Research Data Alliance

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Standardisation of metadata profiles, semantics and ontologies for maximising interoperability.

RDA 21st PLENARY SESSIONS

- Breakout 1: Metadata IG: [Structuring Semantic Information with Respect to Conventional Metadata \(Syntactic\) Structures](#)
- Breakout 1: Data Repository Attributes WG: [Recommended Descriptive Attributes for Data Repositories](#)
- Breakout 1: Software Source Code IG: [Mastering the Art of Research Software Metadata and Metrics](#)
- Breakout 2: Vocabulary Services IG: [Building Collaborative Bridges: Fostering Collaborations within RDA](#)
- Breakout 3: Birds of a Feather: [FAIRification of Genomic Tracks: data-driven life science through granular discovery of biological sequence annotations with uniform metadata](#)
- Breakout 3: Research Data Management in Engineering IG & RDA/CODATA Materials Data, Infrastructure & Interoperability IG: [Engineering Terminology and Schema for LIMS](#)
- Breakout 3: Complex Citations WG: [Complex Citations: Next steps towards a Demonstration Prototype](#)
- Breakout 4: FAIR for Machine Learning (FAIR4ML) IG: [Building towards FAIR for Machine Learning](#)
- Breakout 4: Birds of a Feather: [Let's talk about FAIR mappings! Towards common practices for sharing mappings and crosswalks](#)
- Breakout 6: Birds of a Feather: [Describing Chemical, Physical and Biological samples digitally: Seeking harmonization](#)

 [View the Plenary programme](#)

RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [Agrisemantics WG](#)
- [Blockchain Applications in Health WG](#)
- [Brokering Framework Working Group](#)
- [Complex Citations Working Group](#)
- [Chemistry Research Data IG](#)
- [Data Granularity WG](#)
- [Data policy standardisation and implementation IG](#)
- [Data Repository Attributes WG](#)
- [DMP Common Standards WG](#)
- [FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG](#)
- [FAIR for Machine Learning \(FAIR4ML\) IG](#)
- [Health Data Interest Group](#)
- [Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology WG \(I-ADOPT WG\)](#)
- [Metadata IG](#)
- [Metadata Standards Catalog WG](#)
- [National PID Strategies Interest Group](#)
- [National PID Strategies WG](#)
- [Open Science Graphs for FAIR Data IG](#)
- [Preserving Scientific Annotation WG](#)
- [RDA/CODATA Materials Data, Infrastructure & Interoperability IG](#)
- [Research Data Management in Engineering IG](#)
- [Research Metadata Schemas WG](#)
- [Sensitive Data Interest Group](#)
- [Social Dynamics of Data Interoperability IG](#)
- [Vocabulary Services IG](#)
- [Wheat Data Interoperability WG](#)

 [See all RDA groups](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research](#)
- [39 Hints to Facilitate the Use of Semantics for Data on Agriculture and Nutrition](#)
- [A Fresh Look at FAIR for Research Software](#)
- [A Survey on Adoption Guidelines for the FAIR4RS Principles](#)
- [FAIR Data Maturity Model specification and guidelines](#)
- [FAIR Data Maturity Model specification and guidelines - draft](#)
- [FAIR Principles for Research Software \(FAIR4RS Principles\)](#)
- [Health Research Performing Organisations \(HRPOs\) FAIR Guidelines](#)

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Standardisation of metadata profiles, semantics and ontologies for maximising interoperability.

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS CONT.

- [Member survey on bridging the gap between funders and communities - perspectives on benefits and challenges of FAIR assessments V2.0](#)
- [Metadata Standards Directory Working Group Recommendations](#)
- [Persistent identifiers Consolidated assertions](#)
- [PID Information Types \(PIT\) WG Recommendations](#)
- [Results of an Analysis of Existing FAIR Assessment Tools](#)
- [RDA National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist](#)
- [Summary of Virtual Layer Recommendations](#)
- [The FAIR4RS Team Working Together to Make Research Software FAIR](#)
- [The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations Interlinking Standards, Databases and Data Policies](#)
- [Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things](#)
- [Wheat Data Interoperability Recommendations](#)

 [See all recommendations & outputs](#)

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'Data Lifecycles - Versioning, Provenance, Citation, and Reward'

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Data management topics within the data lifecycle, including description, versioning, provenance, granularity, publishing, citation and reward.

RDA 21st PLENARY SESSIONS

- Breakout 2: Data Discovery Paradigms IG: [Ten recommendations for data repositories/catalogues to improve data discoverability](#)
- Breakout 2: Research Data Architectures in Research Institutions IG: [Data Retention and Disposal infrastructure and policies](#)
- Breakout 2: Ethics and Social Aspects of Data IG: [Identifying and discussing key topics in ethics for the RDA Community: Developing together a revised agenda for the Ethical and Social Aspects of Data \(ESAD\) Interest Group](#)
- Breakout 3: Working with PIDs in Tools IG & National PID Strategies Interest Group: [PID Exchange - a curated information resource for PID adopters](#)
- Breakout 3: Birds of a Feather: [The Way to FAIR: From the instrument to the researcher -- Calibrating the ecosystem](#)
- Breakout 3: Complex Citations WG: [Complex Citations: Next steps towards a Demonstration Prototype](#)
- Breakout 4: Repository Platforms for Research Data IG & Domain Repositories IG: [Data Repositories Discovering Unpublished and Diverse Data Usage and Impact](#)
- Breakout 4: Data Versioning IG: [Revising the Versioning Principles: The Road to Actionable Recommendations](#)
- Breakout 5: RDA-OfR Mapping the landscape of digital research tools WG: [Mapping the landscape of digital research tools working meeting](#)
- Breakout 5: Reproducibility IG: [Introducing the reestablished Reproducibility IG](#)

- Breakout 5: Linguistics Data IG: [Developing a Needs Analysis for Open Scholarship in Linguistics and the Language Sciences](#)
- Breakout 6: Evaluation of Research IG: [Evaluation of Research: Kick-off Plenary Meeting - Community perspectives](#)
- Breakout 6: Birds of a Feather: [Collecting and Managing Data from Citizen Science Research Projects](#)

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RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [CURE-FAIR WG](#)
- [Complex Citations Working Group](#)
- [Data Citation WG](#)
- [Data Discovery Paradigms IG](#)
- [Data Granularity WG](#)
- [Data Usage Metrics WG](#)
- [Data Versioning IG](#)
- [Domain Repositories IG](#)
- [Ethics and Social Aspects of Data IG](#)
- [Evaluation of Research IG](#)
- [FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG](#)
- [Health Data Interest Group](#)
- [Linguistics Data IG](#)
- [National PID Strategies Interest Group](#)
- [Physical Samples and Collections in the Research Data Ecosystem IG](#)
- [Professionalising Data Stewardship IG](#)
- [Repository Platforms for Research Data IG](#)
- [Sharing Rewards and Credit \(SHARC\) IG](#)
- [FAIR Data Maturity Model WG](#)

[★ See all RDA groups](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [23 Things Physical Samples](#)
- [Compilation of Data Versioning Use cases from the RDA Data Versioning Working Group](#)
- [FAIR Principles for Research Software \(FAIR4RS Principles\)](#)
- [Member survey on bridging the gap between funders and communities - perspectives on benefits and challenges of FAIR assessments V2.0](#)

RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

doi. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00094>

'Data Lifecycles - Versioning, Provenance, Citation, and Reward' cont.

Research Data Alliance Pathways

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/rdas-21st-plenary-programme>

Version: July 2023

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Data management topics within the data lifecycle, including description, versioning, provenance, granularity, publishing, citation and reward.

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [Principles and best practices in data versioning for all data sets big and small](#)
- [RDA Data Usage Metrics WG Recommendations](#)
- [The FAIR4RS Team Working Together to Make Research Software FAIR](#)
- [Tromso recommendations for citation of research data in linguistics](#)
- [Versioning Data Is About More than Revisions A Conceptual Framework and Proposed Principles](#)

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THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Implementation of principles and common data management practices from a disciplinary community.

RDA 21st PLENARY SESSIONS

- Breakout 1: Birds of a Feather: [Why aren't we talking about Collections as Data?](#)
- Breakout 1: ESIP/RDA Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences IG: [Where are the FAIR Earth, Space and Environmental Science Discipline Data Repositories?](#)
- Breakout 2: Birds of a Feather: [The RDA Data Rebels Alliance, Transformative Data Futures](#)
- Breakout 3: Birds of a Feather: [FAIRification of Genomic Tracks: data-driven life science through granular discovery of biological sequence annotations with uniform metadata](#)
- Breakout 3: Birds of a Feather: [NTRO Gaggle - Boosting non text support through experiential and collaborative effort](#)
- Breakout 3: Research data needs of the Photon and Neutron Science community IG: [Tools and Methods working towards the FAIR Facility](#)
- Breakout 3: Research Data Management in Engineering IG & RDA/CODATA Materials Data, Infrastructure & Interoperability IG: [Engineering Terminology and Schema for LIMS](#)
- Breakout 5: RDA-OfR Mapping the landscape of digital research tools WG: [Mapping the landscape of digital research tools working meeting](#)
- Breakout 5: Birds of a Feather: [Launching an RDA Domain Ambassadors IG](#)
- Breakout 5: Linguistics Data IG: [Developing a Needs Analysis for Open Scholarship in Linguistics and the Language Sciences](#)

- Breakout 6: Life Science Data Infrastructures IG: [Key aspects of FAIR for infrastructure solutions in the biomolecular life sciences](#)
- Breakout 6: Birds of a Feather: [Describing Chemical, Physical and Biological samples digitally: Seeking harmonization](#)

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RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [Agrisemantics WG](#)
- [Biodiversity Data Integration IG](#)
- [Capacity Development for Agriculture Data WG](#)
- [Chemistry Research Data IG](#)
- [Data Economics IG](#)
- [Discipline-specific Guidance for Data Management Plans WG](#)
- [ESIP/RDA Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences IG](#)
- [Geospatial IG](#)
- [Global Water Information IG](#)
- [Health Data Interest Group](#)
- [Life Science Data Infrastructures IG](#)
- [Linguistics Data IG](#)
- [Neuroimaging Data WG](#)
- [Psychological Data IG](#)
- [Raising FAIRness in health data and health research performing organisations \(HRPOs\) WG](#)
- [RDA / TDWG Metadata Standards for attribution of physical and digital collections stewardship](#)
- [RDA-OfR Mapping the landscape of digital research tools WG](#)
- [RDA COVID-19](#)
- [RDA COVID-19 Epidemiology](#)
- [RDA COVID19-Legal-Ethical](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Clinical](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Community-participation](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Omics](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Social-Sciences](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Software](#)
- [RDA/CODATA Materials Data, Infrastructure & Interoperability IG](#)
- [Reproducible Health Data Services WG](#)

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Implementation of principles and common data management practices from a disciplinary community.

RELEVANT RDA GROUPS CONT.

- [Research Data Management in Engineering IG](#)
- [Research data needs of the Photon and Neutron Science community IG](#)
- [Science communication for research data](#)
- [Small Unmanned Aircraft Systems Data IG](#)
- [Social Science Research Data IG](#)
- [Wheat Data Interoperability WG](#)
- [Working Group on Ethical and Legal best practices for Drone Data in a global research context \(WELDD\)](#)
- [Working with PIDS in Tools](#)

☀ [See all RDA groups](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research](#)
- [23 Things Libraries for Research Data \(Supporting Output\)](#)
- [A Fresh Look at FAIR for Research Software](#)
- [Challenges of Curating for Reproducible and FAIR Research Output](#)
- [Health Research Performing Organisations \(HRPOs\) FAIR Guidelines](#)
- [Member survey on bridging the gap between funders and communities - perspectives on benefits and challenges of FAIR assessments V2.0](#)
- [The FAIR4RS Team Working Together to Make Research Software FAIR](#)
- [The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations Interlinking Standards, Databases and Data Policies](#)

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doi. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00094>

'Discipline Focused Data Issues' cont.

Research Data Alliance Pathways

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/rdas-21st-plenary-programme>

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THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Implementation of principles and common data management practices from a disciplinary community.

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'Research Software'

Research Data Alliance Pathways

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/rdas-21st-plenary-programme>

Version: July 2023

THIS PATHWAY IS ABOUT...

Practices and policies to make software open and FAIR.

RDA 21ST PLENARY SESSIONS

- Breakout 1: Software Source Code IG: [Mastering the Art of Research Software Metadata and Metrics](#)
- Breakout 4: FAIR for Machine Learning (FAIR4ML) IG: [Building towards FAIR for Machine Learning](#)
- Breakout 6: Birds of a Feather: [Policies for Advancing Research Software in Research Performing Organisations](#)
- Breakout 6: Birds of a Feather: [Collecting and Managing Data from Citizen Science Research Projects](#)

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RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS CONT.

- [FAIR4RS Adoption support](#)
 - [Summary of Virtual Layer Recommendations](#)
 - [The FAIR4RS Team Working Together to Make Research Software FAIR](#)
 - [Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things](#)
 - [Use cases and identifier schemes for persistent software source code identification \(V1.1\)](#)
- [See all recommendations & outputs](#)

RELEVANT RDA GROUPS

- [FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG](#)
- [FAIR for Research Software \(FAIR4RS\) WG](#)
- [FAIR for Virtual Research Environments WG](#)
- [RDA-COVID19-Software](#)
- [RDA/WDS Scholarly Link Exchange \(Scholix\) WG](#)
- [Reproducibility IG](#)
- [Software Source Code IG](#)
- [Virtual Research Environment IG \(VRE-IG\)](#)
- [FAIR for Machine Learning \(FAIR4ML\) IG](#)

 [See all RDA groups](#)

RELEVANT OUTPUTS & RECOMMENDATIONS

- [10 Things for Curating Reproducible and FAIR Research](#)
- [A Fresh Look at FAIR for Research Software](#)
- [A Survey on Adoption Guidelines for the FAIR4RS Principles](#)
- [Array Database Assessment Recommendations](#)
- [Challenges of Curating for Reproducible and FAIR Research Output](#)
- [Defining Research Software a controversial discussion](#)
- [FAIR Principles for Research Software \(FAIR4RS Principles\)](#)

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doi. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00094>

Research Data Alliance Pathways: RDA 21st Plenary Synopsis

Version: July 2023

ABOUT THE PATHWAYS

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) Pathways were created by the RDA's [Technical Advisory Board](#) to help community members navigate all RDA activities. This synopsis enhances the [RDA's 21st Plenary](#) experience by providing an overview of all pathways plus their relevant Plenary sessions, RDA groups, recommendations and outputs, and ambassadors.

METHODOLOGY

Machine learning classification and clustering algorithms were employed to map RDA groups, recommendations and outputs, to the Plenary pathways. A text mining exercise was undertaken to assign a list of specific keywords to each Plenary pathway using session application texts submitted by groups in 2019, 2020 and 2021. Group charters and case statement texts, harvested from the RDA website, were mined for these keywords to map groups to the Plenary pathways. Similarly, recommendations and output texts, harvested from the RDA website and Zenodo, were mined for these keywords to map recommendations and outputs to the Plenary pathways. Not all groups, recommendations and outputs were mapped to a Plenary pathway. The data and code generated and analysed are available on [GitHub](#).

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ABOUT THE RDA

The RDA is a global organisation with over 13,000 members from 148 countries that builds social and technical bridges to enable data sharing and reuse.

 [Register to become a member](#)

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